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HOW TO TREAT PUS IN THE EYES OF A CHILD. THE CHILD'S EYES ARE DIM: CAUSES AND WHAT TO DO (TREATMENT)

Annotation: *There are many reasons for the appearance of purulent discharge from the eye. Often this symptom is associated with an infection that is passed from mother to child during childbirth.*

Keywords: *reason, allergies, virus, children, pregnant, blood, symptom.*

A child's eye can become pus-filled for a variety of reasons. Thus, treatment can be started only after the underlying factor has been clearly identified. Parents, on the other hand, should monitor their eyes regularly, follow high-quality hygiene rules, and consult a doctor as soon as the first symptoms are detected. Also read about what medications should be used to treat allergies in children and why strabismus occurs in children. With some diseases in the eyes of children you can observe pus (or exudate). This symptom occurs at different ages from the first week of a child's life. Too often, parents attribute the problem to a "mild infection" and, at best, wash their eyes according to traditional medical prescriptions. Important! According to statistics, in some cases, such an attitude leads to serious problems with vision, including its disappearance. Therefore, if you notice a purulent discharge in the eyes, be sure to show the child to the doctor. Below we focus on children ages 2, 3, and older. Read a separate article on eye pus in newborns. There is also separate material on this symptom in adults. When a child's eyes are swollen, there can be a variety of causes, which can be grouped into four major groups:

Effects of viruses.

Exposure to bacteria.

Allergic reaction.

Dacryocystitis.

The first case is viral conjunctivitis, which can often develop or appear as an independent disease. against the background of influenza or ARVI. In such cases, there is not much pus coming out of the eye and it has a mucous consistency. If caused by adenoviruses, the secretion remains the same, but the child's eyes also become red. For the treatment of such cases may be prescribed poludanum, interferon drops, and for older children - florenal or tebrofen ointment. Herpes conjunctivitis is more dangerous, in which pus accumulates around the eyes and there is a mixture of diarrhea. In this

case, topical administration of acyclovir is often prescribed. If the cause of the discharge is bacteria, treatment with antibiotics is prescribed. In this case, the drug is selected by the treating physician, but only after prior identification of the pathogen and depending on the age and physiological parameters of the patient. Staphylococcal or pneumococcal conjunctivitis. Most often, the discharge of pus occurs with the development of staphylococcal or pneumococcal conjunctivitis. This is explained by untreated angina caused by these microorganisms, as well as by improper treatment, these bacteria spread to the mucous membrane of the eye and provoke the formation of exudate. Newborns are constantly at risk of developing gonococcal conjunctivitis, in which the pus becomes thicker and more, and sometimes leads to the formation of crusts that prevent the opening of the eyes. Usually, this phenomenon is observed already in the first week of life of the baby, and this symptom indicates the need for antibiotic treatment. Allergic pus is almost constantly excreted, the eyes become swollen, red and inflamed. The exudate always comes out of both eyes. First, in such cases, the child's contact with the allergen is limited, after which a course of treatment with antihistamines is carried out. The most common cause of pus in the "childish" eye is called pathology dacryocystitis. This is a violation of the openness of the lacrimal tubules, which open only after the baby comes out of the uterus. But sometimes these canals do not open, and this can be fraught with inflammation of the lacrimal sacs, in which liquid pus content accumulates and occasionally "ruptures". Remember! Dacryocystitis does not require drug treatment, except where local anti-inflammatory drugs are required. The main method of cleaning the tubes is eye massage, and if this procedure does not help, pediatricians perform an examination of the tubules and open them with medical instruments. Basically, the causes of pus removal from the eye are not signs of serious pathologies that require inpatient treatment: it is carried out at home. Exceptions are cases that require urgent surgical intervention. After pre-cleaning the child's eyes of accumulated pus and crusts, the child's parents can independently carry out treatment at home using eye drops and ointments. Cleansing of the eye is carried out by continuous exudation by washing: furatsilin; herbal decoctions; weak (light pink) manganese solution; used tea leaves. Remember! The brewed tea can be used no later than 3 hours after brewing. After this time, substances are formed in the infusion, their penetration into the eyes during rinsing can aggravate the situation. Furatsilin and potassium permanganate are sold freely in pharmacies, however, you can use furatsilin in the form of a ready-made solution or buy tablets in which you need to grind and dissolve yourself in boiled water. Herbal decoction is prepared on the basis of pharmacy chamomile and calendula flowers for washing. A teaspoon is taken from each herb, and this mixture is boiled in 200 milliliters of boiling water, after which it is infused in a water bath for another 10 minutes. Within the next hour, the broth is cooled and filtered. It is better to prepare the product in the morning and use it until the evening - in the morning you need to prepare a new portion of broth. The washing process must be carried out in

accordance with the following rules: Washing is done at least every three hours. Wash your hands thoroughly before the procedure. Only sterile tissue or gauze pad can be used. Pus is removed by removing tissue soaked in the solution from the outer corner of the eye to the inside. Immediately after the procedure, one drop of 0.25% chloramphenicol solution is instilled into each eye. If the discharge is too much, you can put erythromycin ointment instead of drops. In the treatment of the eyes, if there is a purulent discharge, the process should not be aimed solely at relieving the symptoms. Remember! Depending on the additional symptoms that come with the discharge, it is possible to determine the cause of such a painful condition and take appropriate measures to eliminate it. The eyes are red and purulent. If the discharge of pus is accompanied by redness of the conjunctival membrane, the cause may be one of the infectious diseases.

Conjunctivitis. Treatment of such a disease should be combined with the use of antibacterial drops (ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, eubital, actipol, ophthalmoferon) and washing the eyes with a solution of furatsilin or potassium permanganate.

Trachoma. A disease caused by chlamydia. It is a serious pathology and although it is very rare today, there are tools and methods to treat this disease quickly. Treatment is carried out by topical use of antibiotics of the sulfanilamide group (doxycycline, tetracycline, sodium sulfapyridazine, erythromycin).

Barley. In this case, it is better to combine the instillation of sulfanilamide-based solutions with warm compresses based on chamomile or tea tincture. It is enough to moisten the gauze in any of these liquids and apply it on both eyes three times a day for 10-15 minutes. Usually, barley opens itself with normal treatment, but in advanced cases it may require surgery. Sometimes, with infectious diseases, in advanced cases, secondary bacterial infections are associated. Be careful! If the child's eyes are purulent and at the same time have symptoms of a cold - this is probably a weakening of immunity and additional attachment of staphylococcus or streptococcus. Spontaneous treatment is excluded: according to the results of bacterial culture should consult a doctor who prescribes antibiotic treatment. And in parallel, treatment is carried out with topical ophthalmic means. Swollen and swollen eyes are a sign of conjunctivitis, advanced dacryocystitis or keratitis. In this case, dacryocystitis only requires examination, followed by washing of the lacrimal tubules. If keratitis is diagnosed, antibacterial treatment is prescribed in the form of drops or internally (in the latter case, children are prescribed ofloxacin, tetracycline, levofloxacin). Removal of pus from the eye at room temperature is a clear sign of infectious disease, in which the pathogen is also identified and symptomatic and therapeutic treatment of the eye and respiratory organs is prescribed. Attention! If a child has discharge after sleep, it is important to understand that they are a normal product of the activity of the lacrimal glands, which produce excess tear fluid or purulent exudate at night. In the first case, you should not worry, and secondly, first of all, you should visit a pediatrician who will identify the

pathogen through a bacterial vaccine and prescribe treatment. Most of all, a large amount of purulent discharge from the eye after sleep speaks of conjunctivitis, and specialists only need to determine its type and choose a course of treatment.

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